

MANAGING HUMAN RESOURCE DIVERSITY- A TOOL TO GLOBALIZE (A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY)

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Abstract:

This paper examines the extent to which strategic human resource management influences firm performance from various critical perspectives. Rapid environmental changes, competition to provide innovative products and services, changing customer and investor demands and globalization have become the standard backdrop for firms. Sustained competitive advantage could be generated from a firm's human capital by designing strategic human resource management to diagnose a firm's strategic needs which is required to implement a competitive strategy and achieve operational goals.

Keywords: Human resource management, Diversity, Change management, Competitive strategy.

Introduction

What is diversity and what are the goals in achieving a more diverse society? Are there organizations that operate more efficiently with a homogeneous workforce while other organizations are more efficient with a heterogeneous workforce?

This paper critically reviews the literature on managing diversity through human resource management (HRM). We discuss the major issues and objectives of managing diversity and examine the state of human resource diversity management practices in organizations.

By “diversity” we refer here to meaningful differences in co-worker identities –Race, gender, class, age, disability status, sexual orientation, and so on – and their thoughtful leveraging for valued organizational ends. This definition captures three important features of workforce diversity. First, diversity is a characteristic of groups, not individuals. Second, the purposes served by diversity are variable, not fixed, and depend largely on organizational needs and values. Third, few of the possible benefits of diversity are achieved simply through the work

of assembling a diverse group of colleagues. Assembling a diverse group is a necessary step, but only one among several if that diversity is to lift and strengthen your organization. The review reveals limited literature examining how diversity is managed in organizations through effective human resource management. We develop a framework that presents strategies for HR diversity management at the strategic, tactical and operational levels. The review also discusses the implications for practice and further research.

The world's increasing globalization requires more interaction among people from diverse cultures, beliefs and backgrounds than ever before. The society no longer works nor lives in an island; people are now part of the worldwide economy with competition coming from all over the continents. It is because of this reason that profit making, governments and non-profit making organizations need to embrace diversity so as to become more innovative and open to change. Embracing, maximizing and capitalizing on workplace diversity has become an important asset for management today.

HR diversity management practices

HRM is a set of distinctive activities, functions and processes that are aimed attracting, directing and maintaining an organization's human resources (Lado and Wilson 1994).

The HR function has grown substantially over the past few decades and now covers the whole gamut of people management processes. There are different views about the nature of HRM and there exists an enormous variety of HR practices adopted by various organizations. The aim of this paper is to present and analyse how different HRM policies and procedures applied in organisations influence professional development and promotion of women in organisations. The paper will especially analyse four types of policies and procedures and their influence on professional development of women in organisations: equal opportunities, career development opportunities, formalisation of HRM system and work - private life balance. At the end, the paper will present the path for further research.

This paper extends past research and likewise emphasizes the positive influence of HRM on workplace diversity. Changes in the demographics and composition of workforces are

inevitable, which brings along critical challenges for HRM. Organizations vary in their motivation and effort to value diversity. Some organizations truly value diversity, which is also then reflected in their work practices. Other organizations implement diversity initiatives simply to comply with legislation. This approach merely attempts to stop discrimination in the workplace and does not necessarily oblige employers to actively promote diversity. Organizations have to take a stronger stance regarding valuing diversity, which should be reflected in the organizations' culture, design, and policies.(Eugene chew weiliang,2011)

Model of Gender Discrimination

Fig 01

Diversity

Diversity refers to the variety arising out of educational, cultural, racial, ethnic, age, religious and gender differences. The essence of diversity is the acceptance, exploration and leveraging of these differences in a safe, positive and nurturing environment. That means having an open mindset, being inclusive, giving legitimacy to these differences and accepting them with a positive mindset.

India probably has all the world's religions. Many times it is noticed that the culture is very much related to the religious background of the people. People from different geographical area with different cultures, languages, and socio economical background shall be working in the same organization.

Advances in technology and the advent of a global economy bring the people of the world closer together than ever before. Given this fact, businesses, educational systems and other entities are investigating ways to better serve their constituents. This includes being able to attract and retain the best and most qualified workers. Organizations that can develop and employ the necessary policies and procedures to do this will maintain a competitive advantage among their counterparts and increase their effectiveness. To achieve success and maintain a competitive advantage, we must be able to draw on the most important resource such as the skills of the workforce. With the increasing richness of diversity in the workforce, we need to expand our outlook and use creative strategies to be successful. Employees can provide this resource.

Diversity is increasingly recognized and utilized as an important organizational resource in regards to whether the goal is to be an employer of choice, to provide excellent customer service, or to maintain a competitive edge. Workplace diversity is a multi-faceted concept that will continue to evolve as more industries move toward a global marketplace. It also has proven to have led to a perception of being fundamental for employee performance. This fundamental belief forces managers to embrace and comprehend the concept of workplace diversity, its barriers and benefits.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the effect of work force diversify towards employee performance in an organization which focus into air line industry. The research also focuses on workforce diversity which includes the gender, age, ethnic and education background of the employees which is the most critical variables among all the others.

Research objectives

The purpose of this research is to identify whether the variables include gender, age, ethnicity and education background would affect employee performance in an organization.

- To analyse the HR practices in relation to workforce diversity.

- To study the benefits and disadvantages of a diverse workforce to the employees.
- To assess the gender discrimination in work force.
- To study the impact of gender discrimination on employees.
- Understanding key factors that people give more importance.

Literature Review

Human resource management is that part of the management process that specializes in the management of people in work organizations. HRM emphasizes that employees are the primary resource for gaining sustainable competitive advantage, that human resources activities need to be integrated with the corporate strategy, and that human resources specialists help organizational controllers to meet both efficiency and equity objectives.

In theory, the management of people is not different from the management of other resources of organizations. In practice, what makes it different is the nature of the resource, people. Employees differ from other resources because of their ability to evaluate and to question management's actions, and their commitment and cooperation always has to be won. **(Torrington, 1994)**

A global organization depends on people "who are willing to take personal initiative and to co-operate with one another, who have self-confidence and a commitment to the company, and who are able to execute relatively routine tasks with the same proficiency as they are willing to learn new skills and ways to take the company to the next stages of ambition". **(Bartlett and Ghoshal, 1995)**

The globalisation of an organization, therefore, embraces social processes that override the constraints of geography and ethnicity (Levitt, 1983). Its members, no matter where they work, are acculturated to embrace the values and the beliefs of the global organization. This acculturation process is a cognitive event that engages cross-culture interactions to evolve common norms, values, and meanings which provide sustained opportunity for material, political, and symbolic exchange and synergy **(Nahavandi and Maleksadeh, 1988)**.

The HRM function consists of "selecting, rewarding, appraising, socializing, and developing individuals to contribute as much as possible to the achievement of organizational goals" Thus, HRM is acknowledged as a critical dimension of global strategy, as global organizations are venturing into a variety of strategy/structure arrangements that require an

integrated, strategic utilization of human resources, along with financial support and the application of technology. **(Eneroth and Larrson, 1996).**

The world's increasing globalization requires more interaction among people from diverse cultures, beliefs, and backgrounds than ever before. People no longer live and work in an insular marketplace; they are now part of a worldwide economy with competition coming from nearly every continent. For this reason, profit and non-profit organizations need diversity to become more creative and open to change. Maximizing and capitalizing on workplace diversity has become an important issue for management today. Diversity is generally defined as acknowledging, understanding, accepting, valuing and celebrating differences among people with respect to age, class, ethnicity, gender, physical and mental ability, race, sexual orientation, spiritual practice, and public assistance status. Diversity issues are now considered important and are projected to become even more important in the future due to increasing differences in the population of various countries. Companies need to focus on diversity and look for ways to become totally inclusive organizations because diversity has the potential of yielding greater productivity and competitive advantages. **(Ms.Parul Deshwal,2012)**

The concept of diversity refers to a characteristic of a group or organization. It reflects the degree to which there are objective or subjective differences between people within the group (van Knippenberg & Schippers, 2007). Conceptualization of diversity is that of a group characteristic, not an individual characteristic which deals with how differences between group members affect group functioning and performance, not how being different from others affects individual functioning **(Chattopadhyay,2004).**

By managing diversity at the workplace, organizations create an inclusive and harmonious environment which enhances good reputation of the organization with people seeking jobs hence able to attract the best workers in the market. The employees feel valued, rewarded and motivated while working in an organization that manage diversity. According to a research done worldwide three million employees indicated that diversity brings about satisfaction and organizational performance. It was also found out that creating an inclusive and harmonious environment was a key driver in employee engagement and commitment. Managing diversity creates greater employee engagement which at the end leads to reduced labor turnover. **(Tabitha Wangare Wambui,2013)**

Most attention on diversity management focused on the organizational decision maker who is prejudiced against certain groups and who allows these prejudices to influence how he or she treats employee. Moreover, they become embodied in organizational policies and practices that systematically disadvantage some employees. As an extension, employee diversity does not necessarily boost creativity, market share, or competitive advantage. In fact, research suggests that left un-managed, employee diversity is more likely to damage morale, increase turnover, and cause significant communication problems and conflict within the organization (**Loriann and Carol, 2007**)

Tools of managing diversity

The key tool on how to manage diversity in a workplace is planning, implementation and conflict resolution skills. Good communication is one of the best ways to manage diversity in the workplace.

The employees should be encouraged to share concerns as they arise. Every employee should feel equally important to the company. The company should keep an open door policy. Management to be open with their employees so that they feel comfortable coming up with questions and concerns about issues, both non-workrelated and work-related alike, such as diversity. Another vital requirement when dealing with diversity is promoting a 'safe' place for associates to communicate (Koonce, 2001). Social gatherings and business meetings, where every member must listen and have the chance to speak, are good ways to create dialogues. Managers should implement policies such as mentoring programs to provide associates access to information and opportunities. Also, associates should never be denied necessary, constructive, critical feedback for learning about mistakes and successes (Flagg, 2002). Effective managers are aware that certain skills are necessary for creating a successful, diverse workforce. These are; managers must understand discrimination and its consequences and they must recognize their own cultural biases and prejudices (Koonce, 2001). Diversity is not about differences among groups, but rather about differences among individuals. Each individual is unique and does not represent or speak for a particular group. At the same time, managers must be willing to change the organization if necessary (Koonce, 2001).

Organizations need to learn how to manage diversity in the workplace to be successful in the future (Flagg, 2002). According to Roosevelt (2001), managing diversity is a comprehensive process for creating a work environment that includes everyone. When creating a successful diverse workforce, an effective manager should focus on personal awareness. Both managers and associates need to be aware of their personal biases. Therefore, organizations need to develop, implement, and maintain ongoing training because a one-day session of training will not change people's behaviours (Koonce, 2001). Managers must also understand that fairness is not necessarily equality.

Based on the theoretical review we proposed a conceptual model that shows the factors mediating work force strategy & performance link

Fig-02

The role of policies and procedures in human resources management

Based on a large number of researches we can specify four types of HRM policies and procedures relating to professional development of women and generally other social groups: 1) Equal opportunities;
2) Career development;
3) Formalisation of HRM system;

4) Work – Private life balance.

Conclusion

The findings of this study have significant practical implications. The review indicates that there is a continuing need for effective diversity management and for HRM to play an irreplaceable role in this regard. Effective diversity management through good HR practices and procedures leads to positive outcomes. Ineffective diversity management in HR is most likely to result in conflict, demotivation, higher employee turnover and low organizational performance. Therefore, diversity management must become a priority agenda in HRM practices for all organizations. Due to the fact that most organizations consider diversity mainly as an issue of compliance with legal requirements and recruiting ethnic minorities, there is a great need for improved HR diversity strategies focusing on appreciating and making use of diversity.

It can be concluded that workforce diversity is an important topic, which should be of increasing concern for HR managers, as its central objective cannot be separated from business strategy. Moreover, it is important to view diversity from an investment perspective as it allows an organization to determine how to best invest in its people. It is suggested that HR managers must be able to guide organizations through and provide leadership in managing diversity in a way that fully realize the potential benefits that differences can bring. That is, be aware of behaviour and attitudes, acknowledge biases/prejudices, avoid assumptions, and focus on job performance and conduct. This in turn will help the HR manager in his/her substantive activity such as a leadership development and explicit focus on workforce diversity. HRM may be able to achieve these goals through an integrated approach with the combined broader role of organizational management.

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